

FRACTURE BEHAVIOR AND FACE SHEET BUCKLING ANALYSIS OF CFRP/HONEYCOMB SANDWICH PANELS SUBJECTED TO BENDING LOAD

Mae Oiwa ¹, Toshio Ogasawara ¹, Sota Oshima ¹, Takahira Aoki ²

¹ Tokyo University of Agriculture and Technology, ² The University of Tokyo

1. Introduction

CFRP/honeycomb sandwich panel for aircraft interior structures

Face sheet: CFRP[90/0], t=0.3 mm
Core: Nomex honeycomb, h=10.3 mm

Failure process

- (1) Local buckling of face sheet
 - Type I : outward / specimen edge
 - Type II : outward / middle of specimen
 - Type III : inward / specimen edge
- (2) Debonding between face sheet and core
- (3) Crack propagation of face sheet

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High speed observation (Flame rate 8 ms)

Objective

Establishment of bending strength prediction methodology of CFRP / honeycomb sandwich panels for aircraft interior structures

2. Stress and Buckling Analysis Model

- Detailed honeycomb structures were modeled in the middle part of a beam where the face sheet local buckling occurred, and solid elements were used for the other parts.
- Equivalent elastic properties of the honeycomb core were applied to the solid element.

3. Equivalent Stiffness of Honeycomb Core

- Homogenized elastic properties were determined by FEA.
- Periodic boundary conditions (PBC) were applied to the unit cell model of the honeycomb core.
- Multi point constraint (MPC) was utilized for surfaces, edges and vertexes.

4. Analysis Results

Stress analysis

- Calculated bending stiffness showed good agreement with the experimental results (Relative error was approximately 1.1 %).

Buckling eigenvalue analysis

- Each buckling mode corresponded to the experimentally observed local buckling behavior.
- Calculated buckling load also well agreed with the bending strength of the sandwich panels.

(a) outward / specimen edge

(b) inward / specimen edge

(c) outward / middle of specimen

Buckling mode	Buckling eigenvalue analysis			Experimental	
	Eigen value	Buckling Load, [N]	Displacement [mm]	Failure Load, [N]	Displacement [mm]
Specimen edge (outwards)	0.738	660	30.6	635	29.3
Specimen edge (inwards)	0.742	664	30.8	646	29.5
Middle of a specimen	0.807	722	33.5	719	32.5

5. Conclusion

In order to establish the bending strength prediction methodology of CFRP / honeycomb sandwich panels for aircraft interior structures, stress and buckling analyses using FEA were conducted. The following conclusions were obtained.

1. Load-displacement diagram calculated using the stress analysis well agreed with the experimental results. Therefore, the effectiveness of the FE model and the equivalent stiffness of the honeycomb core were demonstrated.
2. Buckling modes calculated by the buckling eigenvalue analysis corresponded to the experimentally observed local buckling behavior. In addition, the buckling load and the displacement at each eigenvalue also showed good agreement with the experimental results.